

Work Engagement Mediation to Optimize the State Civil Apparatus Performance

Pandapotan Na Uli Sun Siregar¹, Dearma Sariyani Sinaga², Jenni Tarigan³, Jonner Lumban Gaol⁴,
Runggu Besmandala Napitupulu^{5*}

^{1,2,3,4,5}Universitas Darma Agung, Medan, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This research aims to investigate the effect of self-efficacy on work engagement and the influence of both constructs on the performance of the state civil apparatus at the tourism office of North Sumatra province. The target population was 269 people. The sample was set at 200 people, their opinions were collected using cluster random sampling techniques. Primary data were processed using a structural equation model supported by the lisrel application program. Self-efficacy affects work engagement and the performance of state civil apparatus. Work engagement affects employee performance. Work engagement fully mediates the effect of self-efficacy on the state civil apparatus performance. The leadership of the tourism office of North Sumatra province is important to pay attention to work enthusiasm, especially enthusiasm when working to enhance work quality.

KEYWORDS: Mediation, Optimize, Self-efficacy, State civil apparatus performance, Work engagement

INTRODUCTION

Leaders in various agencies including government agencies such as section heads, department heads, division heads, or department heads, and other leaders must continue to instill the agency's goals in their subordinates. The agency's performance as a result of the organization team teamwork or members' efforts is shown by the realization of the budget. There are three budget targets and realization for an activities series at the North Sumatra Tourism Office, namely: Fostering arts and culture, preserving arts and culture, and cultural heritage; Increasing the number of tourist visits to North Sumatra; Increasing cooperation and improving the tourism industry.

The budget target for the activities of fostering arts and culture, preserving arts and culture, and cultural heritage is Rp7,539,232,419 with a realization of Rp6,747,220,574. So the achievement is 89.6%. The budget target for the activity of increasing the number of tourist visits to North Sumatra is Rp14,138,023,308 with a realization of Rp12,079,514,082. The achievement is 85.4%. The budget for activities to increase cooperation in, the tourism industry and increase the tourism human resources competence has a target of Rp1,952,222,550. The achievement of this activity budget is 96%.

The budget realization of the three activities on average has only reached 90.3% or has not yet met the target of 100% and there is still a remainder of around 9.7%. The target and budget realization of the three series of activities above can be more clearly compared in Figure 1

Figure 1. Budget Target and Realization

Source: secondary data, 2023

The achievement of tourism administration services is 90 from a standard of 110. So this standard has not been achieved. The realization of the adequacy of infrastructure in the field is 100 from a standard of 110. Not yet achieved but better than the fulfillment of the first standard. The implementation of routine reports is 100 from a standard of 110. So it has not been achieved.

Two activities that have reached the standard are: Security/comfort and Togetherness among staff. The highest achievement of 120 is in the second one. The achievements and standards of the activities are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Bar graph of activity standards achievements

Source: Department of Tourism, 2023

The achievement in the human resource performance index is presented in Figure 2. Information obtained from the initial survey shows that several aspects have not been achieved including administrative services, supporting infrastructure to get to tourist destinations, and routine reports. If observed, two aspects have been met, namely Security/comfort and Togetherness between staff. However, overall it appears that the State Civil Apparatus has not shown what is expected. Therefore, it is not surprising that the performance of the State Civil Apparatus is considered less than optimal.

In this study, the performance that is still less than optimal wants to be improved. The question is how to improve it. Therefore, variables that influence the endogenous variables are needed. Referring to several previous studies, it can be concluded that human resource performance is influenced by self-efficacy (Ramadhan et al., 2022; Çetin & Aşkun, 2018) and work engagement (Savitri, 2023; Lakshmi Narayanamma et al., 2022). In addition, other researchers say that work engagement is also influenced by self-efficacy (Asikin & Burhan, 2021; Tyas et al., 2020). However, the above propositions are still doubtful, because not all research results are in line with the above proposition where work engagement does not affect employee performance (Mughal, 2020). Therefore, it can be retested through this study.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

A. Literature review

In this section, the author conducts conceptual synthesis by formulating the definition of empirical concepts referring to the concepts put forward by previous authors. Furthermore, it is operationalized according to the empirical conditions of the research. Operationalization becomes dimensions to indicators and finally in the form of statement items.

The research concept synthesis results are presented below. Employee performance is an individual achievement that is the result of work in carrying out assigned tasks based on the abilities possessed, experience, sincerity, and accuracy (time) by organizational goals. (Kinicki, 2021; Colquitt et al., 2021; Torrington et al., 2020; Pawar, 2020; Carbery & Cross, 2019).

Work engagement is a strong and deep desire to work and serve in the organization's efforts to achieve its goals. (DuBrin, 2019; Carbery & Cross, 2019; Bhalla, 2018; Deepa et al., 2014; Holbeche & Matthews, 2012).

Self-efficacy is an individual's belief in mobilizing affective, cognitive, and psychomotor abilities so that they can complete a task, achieve the goals set, and carry them out optimally. (Robbins & Judge, 2022; Luthans et al., 2021; Tyas et al., 2020; DuBrin, 2019; Haddad & Taleb, 2016).

B. Hypotheses Development

The conceptual framework in this study is built in the form of a model consisting of propositions (Sugiyono, 2017). The causal relationship between the concepts of the synthesis results in constructs contained in the proposition. The conceptual framework will be confirmed through the results of relevant previous studies.

Individuals feel confident in their ability to achieve something determined by the term self-efficacy. This strong belief will have a positive impact on achieving organizational goals. The research results by Ardi et al., (2017) show that there is an influence of self-efficacy on employee engagement with a weight of 61.9%; There is an influence of self-efficacy on employee performance of 43.1%; The impact of employee engagement on employee performance. 41.4%; Through employee engagement, self-efficacy has an indirect effect on employee performance of 25.6%.

The results of the research analysis in Hadi, (2023) are: Self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on employee performance; Work motivation mediates the relationship between self-efficacy and employee performance positively and significantly; Work engagement mediates the positive and significant relationship between self-efficacy and employee performance.

The following two research results also show that self-efficacy affects employee engagement (Asikin & Burhan, 2021; Tyas et al., 2020). If employee self-efficacy is higher, then their engagement in their work increases. The study resulted by Lusiferina & Utami, (2023) shows that self-efficacy and organizational support have a significant effect on employee performance. This study also shows that self-efficacy and organizational support have a significant effect on employee engagement, and employee engagement has a significant effect on employee performance. Employee engagement can mediate the influence of self-efficacy and organization on employee performance. Based on the descriptions that have been put forward by the authors above, hypothesis 1 is proposed,

H1: There is an influence of self-efficacy on state civil apparatus work engagement.

A person's self-confidence will be able to mobilize his/her affective, cognitive, and psychomotor abilities to complete a job will have an impact on achieving organizational goals. This self-efficacy construct is very important for human resources in an organization. Increasing self-efficacy is expected to improve employee performance.

Çetin & Aşkun, (2018) the results of their research show that the results of the multilevel analysis confirm the hypothesis which shows that performance is influenced by self-efficacy, teamwork, and intrinsic motivation, functioning as a partial mediator in this relationship, namely intrinsic motivation.

A longitudinal field study was conducted by Carter et al., (2018) in an Australian financial services firm. Using survey data linked to objectively measured performance, it was found that the additive effects of employee self-efficacy and engagement explained 12% of appointments made and 39% of products sold over past performance.

These findings suggest that human resource management practitioners should pay attention to employee self-efficacy and engagement to improve employee performance while encouraging researchers to combine both measures when conducting performance studies.

Ramadhan et al., (2022) obtained findings from their research results that self-efficacy has a positive effect on employee performance with a significance level of $0.047 < 0.05$. Employee engagement has a positive effect on employee performance with a significance level of $0.015 < 0.05$. Both of these constructs affect employee performance.

The results are in line with those found in several studies such as Sidik Nusannas et al., (2020); Lisbona et al., (2018); Haddad & Taleb, (2016) stated that self-efficacy affects performance. Based on the description above, the researcher proposes hypothesis 2

H2: There is an influence of self-efficacy on state civil apparatus performance.

Employee engagement has become a top business priority for senior executives. In this fast-paced economy, business leaders recognize that having a high-performing workforce is critical to growth and survival. Markey, (2016) realized that a highly engaged workforce can increase innovation, productivity, and bottom-line performance while reducing the costs associated with recruitment and retention in a highly competitive talent market.

Tanwar, (2017) said that the construct of employee engagement is built on the foundation of concepts such as organizational citizenship behavior, employee commitment, and job satisfaction. Aziez, (2022) target achievement, quality, and quantity are performance behaviors. Improving an employee's work skills will make him work better and, in turn, will improve his performance.

Optimal performance achievement is one of the impacts of work engagement. It's very useful in creating productivity both individually and in groups or organizations. Increased performance will have an impact on financial support. Jagannathan, (2014) has conducted a causal study approach to study the relational impact. The elements of employee involvement have been identified. Employee performance is influenced by employee engagement.

Several studies that have been conducted have shown that work engagement affects performance, including (Savitri, 2023; Lakshmi Narayanamma et al., 2022; Aiyub et al., 2021; Pitaloka & Putri, 2021; Bale & Pillay, 2021; Sugianingrat et al., 2019; Muller & Smith, 2018; Kumar et al., 2014). Based on the description above, the author proposes hypothesis 3,

H3: There is an influence of work engagement on state civil apparatus performance.

Several previous studies have shown that work engagement is a mediator of self-efficacy on employee performance. These two propositions have been revealed from the research results of Ardi et al., (2017) and Hadi, (2023). The research model is built by the constructs of efficacy, work involvement, and human resource performance. The three constructs are in a communality. If the three constructs influence each other recursively, then work engagement can mediate the influence of self-efficacy on employee performance. Referring to the description above, the authors propose hypothesis 4.

H4: Work engagement mediates the influence of self-efficacy on the state civil apparatus performance

METHODS

Exploratory and causal designs are applied in this research (Hair et al., 2020; Burns & Veeck, 2020). Causal design means that the authors want to discuss the influence of exogenous constructs on endogenous ones both directly and indirectly. Hypothesis development refers to exploratory design.

The target population is the State Civil Apparatus at the Tourism Office of North Sumatra Province as many as 269 people. The number of samples taken was 200 people with a cluster random sampling technique. Primary data was processed using structural equation model analysis techniques with the Lisrel software supported, using the weighted least squares estimation method. (Whittaker & Schumacker, 2022 ; Wijanto, 2008; Diamantopoulos & A.Siguaw, 2000).

The constructs in the research model are measured through indicators or statement items with a Likert scale (1-5). A good measurement model has Discriminant Validity, $\Phi \leq 0$; Standard factor loading > 0.50 , and ideal ≥ 0.70 where Z-value ≥ 1.96 ; Construct reliability includes: Composite reliability, $CR \geq 0.70$ and average extracted variance, $AVE > 0.50$. A good structural model has met the goodness of fit index (GOF) (Geiser, 2021; Hair et al., 2019; Collier, 2020; Byrne, 2016).

In general, the structural equation model can be written as follows:

- General equation of the exogenous construct measurement model: $\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{\Lambda}_x \xi + \delta$ 1
- General equation of the endogenous construct measurement model: $\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{\Lambda}_y \eta + \varepsilon$ 2
- General equation of the structural model: $\eta = \mathbf{B}\eta + \mathbf{\Gamma}\xi + \zeta$ 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Primary data processing with structural equation modeling (SEM) through the support of the Lisrel application program produces a research path diagram model and functional form, namely structural equations. The path diagram of the research model that has

been fit as presented in Figure 3 includes a first-order measurement model, a second-order measurement model, and finally a hybrid model that shows the causal relationship among the three constructs.

A. Dominant Indicators and Dimensions.

From the path diagram, indicator paths that reflect each dimension can be seen on the right side. Dimensions that reflect each construct are on the left side. The dominant level dimension (X1) is reflected by the indicator of completing difficult tasks (X13) with a standardized loading factor (SLF) = 0.94. The strength dimension (X2) is reflected by the dominant motivation/energy indicator (X21) and leader/colleague support (X22) with an SLF of 0.92 each. The generalization dimension (X3) is reflected by the dominant belief indicator to solve problems in all conditions (X32) with SLF = 0.95.

The vigor dimension (Y1) is predominantly reflected by the indicator of feeling enthusiastic when working (Y13) with SLF = 0.92. The dedication dimension (Y2) is predominantly reflected by the indicator of feeling enthusiastic and proud of one's work (Y21) with SLF = 0.96. The absorption dimension (Y3) is predominantly reflected by the indicator of feeling something is missing when not coming to work (X32) with SLF = 0.91.

Chi-Square=743.61, df=334, P-value=0.00000, RMSEA=0.079

Figure 3. Path diagram of the fit research model (standardized solution)

Source: Processed from primary data, 2023

The Quantity Dimension (Z1) is predominantly reflected by the indicator of feeling enthusiastic when working (Z12) with SLF = 0.96. The Quality Dimension (Z2) is predominantly reflected by the accuracy indicator (Z21) with SLF = 0.96. The Initiative Dimension (Z3) is predominantly reflected by the indicators of not waiting for orders (Z31) and readiness (Z32) each having SLF = 0.95. The Creativity Dimension (Z4) is predominantly reflected by the indicator of mastery of work techniques (Z42) with SLF = 0.96. The Reliability Dimension (Z5) is predominantly reflected by the indicator of Patience and Diligence (Z52) with SLF = 0.94.

The dominant self-efficacy construct is reflected by the Strength dimension (X2) with SLF = 0.96. The dominant work engagement construct is reflected by the Vigor dimension (Y1) with SLF = 0.95. The dominant employee performance construct is reflected by the quality dimension (Z2) with SLF = 0.98.

The path diagram (standardized solution) above has provided information about the residual measurement model, SLF indicators and dimensions, and the weight of influence among constructs. Two functional equations are presented to complete the information on the research results, namely structural equation models I and II as presented below.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{TERKAIT} &= 0.80 * \text{EFIKASI}, \text{Errorvar.} = 0.37, R^2 = 0.63 \dots\dots\dots 4 \\ &\quad (0.093) \\ &\quad \quad 8.59 \\ \text{KINERJA} &= 0.56 * \text{TERKAIT} + 0.21 * \text{EFIKASI}, \text{Errorvar.} = 0.46, R^2 = 0.54 \dots\dots\dots 5 \\ &\quad (0.12) \qquad \qquad (0.11) \\ &\quad \quad 4.71 \qquad \qquad \quad 1.99 \end{aligned}$$

B. Structural Equation Model I

The weight of the direct influence of self-efficacy (EFIKASI) on work engagement (TERKAIT) is 0.80, standard deviation = 0.093 with z-value = 8.59 > 1.96 means significant with a 95% confidence level of the two-tailed test. Self-efficacy has a significant and positive effect on work engagement. Changes in exogenous constructs are in line with changes in endogenous constructs. If self-efficacy increases by 1 unit, there will be an increase in work engagement of 0.80 units. Conversely, if there is a decrease in self-efficacy by 1 unit, then work engagement will decrease by 0.80 units.

Residual equation 4 = 0.37 < 4.00, acceptable, and Rsquare = 0.63 > 0.50, significant model (Hair et al., 2019). Changes in self-efficacy covariance are found in changes in work engagement covariance of 0.63 (Rsquare > Errorvar) Exogenous constructs are dominant in determining exogenous constructs. The remaining 0.37 comes from external factors of structural equation model I or equation 4. This structural model can be used for confirmation and prediction purposes. In other words, it is suitable for further discussion.

C. Structural Equation Model II

The weight of the direct influence of work engagement on the state civil apparatus performance (KINERJA) is 0.56, with standard deviation = 0.12 with z-value = 4.71 > 1.96 means significant with a 95% confidence level of the two-tailed test. Work engagement has a significant and positive effect on state civil apparatus performance. Changes in exogenous constructs are in line with changes in endogenous constructs. If work involvement increases by 1 unit, there will be an increase in state civil apparatus performance of 0.56 units, assuming constant self-efficacy. Conversely, if there is a decrease in work involvement by 1 unit, then state civil apparatus performance will decrease by 0.56 units, assuming no change in self-efficacy.

The weight of the direct influence of self-efficacy on state civil apparatus performance is 0.21, with standard deviation = 0.11 with z-value = 1.99 > 1.96 means significance with a 95% confidence level of a two-tailed test. Self-efficacy has a significant and positive effect on state civil apparatus performance. Changes in exogenous constructs are in line with changes in endogenous constructs. If self-efficacy increases by 1 unit, there will be an increase in state civil apparatus performance of 0.21 units, assuming constant work engagement. Conversely, if there is a decrease in self-efficacy by 1 unit, then state civil apparatus performance will decrease by 0.21 units, assuming no change in work engagement.

The influence of work engagement on state civil apparatus performance is stronger than self-efficacy. The influence of self-efficacy is stronger on work engagement than on state civil apparatus performance. The residual of structural model II is 0.46 < 4.00, acceptable, and Rsquare = 0.54 > 0.50, a significant model. Both exogenous constructs dominantly contribute to state civil

apparatus performance, compared to elements from outside equation 5. Structural equation model II can be used for confirmation and prediction purposes. In other words, it is worthy of use for further studies. Rsquare equation 4 is greater than Rsquare equation 5. This means that the confirmation and prediction of structural equation model I are more accurate than structural equation model II.

D. Work engagement mediation

In addition to the confirmation of previous research results, the three constructs are in a communality, where there is a recursive relationship. Thus, there is an indirect influence of the self-efficacy construct on the state civil apparatus performance through work engagement. An intervening variable is called a mediator if the z-value > 1.96 at $\alpha = 0.05$ 2-tailed test.

The weight of the indirect influence of self-efficacy on state civil apparatus performance through work engagement is 0.44. Standard deviation = 0.10 with z-value = 4.42 > 1.96, meaning significant with a 95% confidence level of 2-tailed test. Work engagement is a mediator of self-efficacy on state civil apparatus performance.

Indirect effects and direct effects on the same path are important to note. Is the program or policy better directed directly to state civil apparatus performance or directed first to the intermediate construct or mediator? The comparison between indirect effects and direct effects is presented in Table 1

Table 1. Indirect Effect and Direct Effect Comparison

Indirect Effect (IE)		Direct Effect (DE)		Comparison	The nature of mediation
Path	Weight	Path	Weight		
EFIKASI → TERKAIT → KINERJA	0.44	EFIKASI → KINERJA	0.21	IE > DE	Full mediation

Source: Primary data, 2023

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the indirect effect of self-efficacy on state civil apparatus performance through work engagement (EFIKASI → TERKAIT → KINERJA) is stronger than the direct effect of self-efficacy on state civil apparatus performance (EFIKASI → KINERJA). Work engagement can increase the effect of self-efficacy on endogenous constructs. This fact is called full mediation.

CONCLUSION, IMPLICATION, RECOMMENDATION, AND LIMITATION

A. Conclusion

Self-efficacy specifically strength, more specifically motivation/energy plays a role in increasing work engagement and performance of state civil apparatus in the tourism office of North Sumatra province. Work engagement specifically vigor, more specifically feeling enthusiastic when working plays a role in increasing the performance of state civil apparatus. Self-efficacy plays a role in increasing the performance of state civil apparatus specifically work quality and, more specifically work accuracy.

B. Implication

Work engagement is dominant in improving the performance of state civil apparatus. Therefore, the head of the North Sumatra provincial tourism office is important to pay attention to work enthusiasm, especially enthusiasm when working on improving work quality, especially work accuracy.

C. Recommendation

The head of the North Sumatra provincial tourism office should pay more attention to work enthusiasm to improve the state civil apparatus performance. Future researchers can add relevant exogenous constructs to improve the state civil apparatus performance because external factors in the model that contribute to state civil apparatus performance are still relatively large, namely 46%.

D. Limitation

The information revealed by the study only applies to the North Sumatra Province Tourism Office. Therefore, it is not relevant as a benchmark for other provinces in Indonesia. In addition, the data used is cross-sectional, so it only applies when employee opinions are collected. The information obtained may not be the same in the past and the future.

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